

Leveraging ChatGPT to Transform English Language Teaching

Haekal Fikri

Universitas Negeri Makassar

220025301052@student.unm.ac.id

<https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=UY7cJNkAAAAJ>

ABSTRACT

In recent years, English language teaching has undergone significant transformations owing to technological advancements and the integration of innovative pedagogical approaches. Among these advancements, the incorporation of chatbots and conversational agents in educational settings has garnered considerable attention. ChatGPT, an advanced language model based on the GPT-3.5 architecture developed by OpenAI, has emerged as a promising tool for enhancing language learning experiences. The study obtained articles by conducting searches using internet search engines such as Google Scholar and ERIC, specifically focusing on ChatGPT integration in English language teaching. This approach was chosen to meet the paper's objective, employing inclusion and exclusion criteria. The analysis results showed that the potential impact of ChatGPT on the landscape of English Language Teaching and Learning is immense, as it exhibits the ability to comprehend intricate queries, generate plausible responses, and offer personalized assistance. Striking a balance between AI and human engagement is crucial, as teachers play a pivotal role in nurturing critical thinking and social skills in students.

Keywords: *ChatGPT, Artificial Intelligence, English Language Teaching*

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, English language teaching has undergone significant transformations owing to technological advancements and the integration of innovative pedagogical approaches. Among these advancements, the incorporation of chatbots and conversational agents in educational settings has garnered considerable attention. ChatGPT, an advanced language model based on the GPT-3.5 architecture developed by OpenAI, has emerged as a promising tool for enhancing language learning experiences (AI, 2022). Traditionally, language learning has relied on face-to-face interactions, textbooks, and classroom activities. However, with the advent of artificial intelligence and natural language processing, the boundaries of language education have expanded significantly (Gupta & Muddgal, 2022). Moreover, ChatGPT presents a unique opportunity to simulate human-like conversations, engage learners in authentic language use, and provide personalized feedback (Caulfield, 2023). Leveraging vast amounts of data from diverse sources, the model demonstrates the ability to generate coherent and contextually appropriate responses, making it a potentially valuable resource for language learners.

The integration of chatbots and conversational agents in language education has attracted considerable attention in recent years (Belda, 2022). These technological advancements offer a range of potential benefits, including 24/7 accessibility, personalized instruction, and ample opportunities for practice and feedback (Mageira et al., 2022). Particularly, the impressive conversational capabilities of ChatGPT make it a promising tool for English language teaching. However, a comprehensive examination of the existing research on the application of ChatGPT in language education is essential to fully grasp its impact and implications. The utilization of chatbots and conversational agents in language education has sparked significant interest due to the advantages they bring (Wahyuni, 2022). One notable advantage is the flexibility they offer, enabling learners to access language learning resources and support at any time. Unlike traditional classroom settings with time and location limitations, chatbots and

conversational agents empower learners to engage with language learning materials at their convenience, fostering a learner-centered and flexible approach.

Another advantage lies in the potential for personalized instruction. ChatGPT, with its advanced language processing capabilities, can tailor its responses and feedback to meet the unique needs of individual learners (Alnaqbi & Fouda, 2023). By analyzing learners' input, ChatGPT can provide customized guidance, addressing specific challenges and adapting the learning experience to cater to different learning styles. This personalized approach enhances learner engagement, motivation, and overall learning outcomes. Furthermore, chatbots and conversational agents offer abundant opportunities for practice and feedback (Fitria, 2023). Learners can engage in interactive conversations with ChatGPT, allowing them to practice their speaking and writing skills in a supportive environment. The immediate and constructive feedback provided by ChatGPT aids learners in identifying and correcting language errors, facilitating continuous improvement. Moreover, the repetitive nature of interactions with chatbots enables learners to reinforce their language knowledge and skills through consistent practice, which is crucial for effective language acquisition (Baidoo-Anu & Owusu Ansah, 2023).

The distinct feature of ChatGPT lies in its ability to engage in conversations that closely resemble human dialogue. ChatGPT produces responses that mimic human speech patterns through natural language generation capabilities, creating an authentic and immersive language practice environment (Farrokhnia et al., 2023). This feature holds great potential for developing learners' communicative competence by providing realistic language interactions and fostering the development of conversational skills. However, despite the promising outlook, conducting a systematic analysis of existing research on the application of ChatGPT in language education is imperative to comprehend its impact and implications fully. This review aims to critically examine the literature to uncover the potential, limitations, challenges, and attitudes associated with incorporating ChatGPT into English language teaching.

METHOD

The study obtained articles by conducting searches using internet search engines such as Google Scholar and ERIC, specifically focusing on ChatGPT integration in English language teaching. This approach was chosen to meet the paper's objective, employing inclusion and exclusion criteria. The inclusion criteria for articles are as follows:

- 1) The research is based on empirical evidence.
- 2) The publication year falls within the range of 2023.
- 3) The research represents perspectives from different countries.
- 4) The first theme's keyword is "potential of ChatGPT in English language teaching."
- 5) The second theme's keyword is "limitations and challenges of ChatGPT."
- 6) The third theme's keyword is "attitudes toward ChatGPT."
- 7) The resulting articles will be carefully examined and categorized into subthemes for analysis.
- 8) The context is education within the field of English language teaching.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Potential ChatGPT in English Language Teaching

The literature review reveals several studies that examine the potential of ChatGPT in English Language Teaching (ELT), highlighting its transformative capabilities in education. Zhu et al. (2023) emphasize the transformative potential of ChatGPT, emphasizing its ability to comprehend complex queries and assist with complex tasks. However, it also acknowledges the limitations of ChatGPT, such as the production of inaccurate or biased information. Despite these limitations, researchers suggest conducting a thorough SWOT analysis (strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, threats) to effectively harness ChatGPT's potential in education. In line with the potential benefits of ChatGPT in ELT, Qureshi (2023) discusses the advantages of incorporating ChatGPT as a learning and assessment tool in undergraduate Computer Science curricula. This integration enhances student

involvement, cooperation, accessibility, and availability, ultimately leading to improved scores. However, the study also recognizes the challenges and opportunities presented by the integration of AI in higher education.

Furthermore, Herbold et al. (2023) compare ChatGPT-generated essays with human-written essays, revealing that AI models like ChatGPT can outperform humans in generating argumentative essays. This finding supports the idea that ChatGPT can assist students in improving their writing skills, which is a vital aspect of English language learning. Fauzi et al. (2023) enumerate various ways in which ChatGPT can assist students, such as providing information, improving language skills, facilitating collaboration, increasing efficiency, and providing support and motivation. This study aligns with the potential benefits of ChatGPT in ELT, emphasizing its role in enhancing learning experiences and supporting language development.

However, it is crucial to consider the ongoing debates and drawbacks associated with the use of ChatGPT in language teaching and learning. Kohnke et al. (2023) highlight the importance of teachers and learners possessing digital competencies to use ChatGPT effectively and ethically. This finding underscores the need for responsible implementation and teacher training to ensure the successful integration of ChatGPT into ELT practices. By considering these findings together, it becomes evident that ChatGPT holds significant potential to bring about transformative changes in ELT. It can assist students in developing their language skills, enhance engagement and collaboration, and provide personalized learning experiences. However, to fully harness its benefits, it is essential to address the limitations and challenges associated with ChatGPT and ensure that teachers and learners possess the necessary digital competencies for its ethical and effective use in ELT.

3.2 Limitations and Challenges ChatGPT

The limitations and challenges of ChatGPT can be succinctly summarized based on the pertinent findings from the aforementioned studies. A notable constraint of ChatGPT pertains to its inability to generate visual content, as underscored in the study conducted by Deshpande and Szefer (2023). The researchers discerned that ChatGPT encounters difficulties when confronted with queries involving diagrams or figures, thereby substantially circumscribing its capacity to provide visually-driven explanations or responses. This shortcoming represents a formidable challenge in domains reliant on visual representations, such as geometry or technical disciplines where diagrams are pervasive. Consequently, ChatGPT's efficacy and versatility in these areas are decidedly constrained. Moreover, the investigation carried out by Wardat et al. (2023) unveiled another limitation pertaining to ChatGPT's ability to rectify misconceptions, particularly within the domain of geometry. The researchers observed that although ChatGPT performs reasonably well in generating solutions, it frequently falls short in effectively addressing and rectifying misconceptions harbored by students. This limitation poses a hindrance to its potential as a comprehensive educational tool, as it may not furnish accurate or insightful feedback in cases where students have misconstrued fundamental concepts.

In conjunction with the constraints associated with content generation, concerns regarding the academic integrity implications of ChatGPT have been raised by Perkins (2023). Perkins elucidates that large language models (LLMs) like ChatGPT possess the capacity to circumvent extant detection methodologies, thereby presenting a momentous challenge in upholding academic integrity. This implies that students can potentially utilize ChatGPT to fabricate original, coherent text that may elude traditional plagiarism detection systems. Consequently, it is imperative for academic institutions to revise their policies and detection mechanisms to effectively address the utilization of LLMs like ChatGPT, thereby ensuring equitable evaluation and the preservation of academic integrity. Similarly, (Joshi et al., 2023) caution against excessive reliance on ChatGPT for the completion of assignments and examinations in undergraduate computer science

courses. They emphasize that while ChatGPT can proffer assistance, students who unthinkingly rely on it run the risk of impeding their progress by failing to actively engage with the course material or cultivate critical thinking skills. This underscores the significance of striking a balance between harnessing the capabilities of ChatGPT and fostering independent learning among students, thereby promoting comprehensive knowledge acquisition.

These limitations and challenges assume paramount importance when contemplating the implementation of ChatGPT within educational settings. While it undeniably offers invaluable assistance in generating written content and supporting various educational tasks, the limitations surrounding content generation, potential threats to academic integrity, and the imperative of fostering students' independent learning ought to be duly addressed. Future advancements should focus on enhancing ChatGPT's aptitude for handling visual content and furnishing accurate feedback, thereby bolstering its efficacy as an educational tool. Additionally, academic institutions must institute unambiguous guidelines and policies to effectively address the ethical employment of LLMs within educational environments, thus ensuring an equitable and responsible pedagogical experience.

3.3 Attitude toward ChatGPT in ELT

The attitude toward ChatGPT in the context of English Language Teaching (ELT) has been the subject of investigation in various studies, shedding light on both the potential benefits and the challenges associated with integrating ChatGPT into educational settings. Ali et al. (2023) conducted a study that revealed a generally positive attitude among learners towards ChatGPT, as it served as a motivator for the development of their reading and writing skills. However, the learners exhibited a more neutral stance regarding its impact on listening and speaking skills. This suggests that while ChatGPT holds promise for certain language competencies, its effectiveness in fostering oral communication skills, which are crucial in language learning, may be limited.

In the realm of educators, Halaweh (2023) explored the potential of ChatGPT as a valuable tool in teaching and research contexts. This study emphasized the importance of responsible implementation and an awareness of the potential risks associated with ChatGPT. To ensure its successful integration into educational settings, strategies and techniques were proposed to mitigate these risks and promote responsible usage. Moreover, Chinonso et al. (2023) underscored the transformative potential of ChatGPT in revolutionizing education. They highlighted its ability to provide personalized learning experiences, automate repetitive tasks, and enable teachers to focus on more essential aspects of instruction. This aligns with the notion that ChatGPT can enhance productivity and improve learning efficiency.

In terms of ethical considerations, Cannon (2023) emphasized the responsible and ethical use of ChatGPT in the classroom. The study suggested that ChatGPT can serve as a valuable tool to help students develop comfort with conversational AI and foster an understanding of the ethical implications associated with its use. Additionally, ChatGPT was found to contribute to the development of critical thinking skills and promote awareness of the broader implications of artificial intelligence in everyday life. Nevertheless, Alnaqbi and Fouda (2023) raised practical and ethical concerns regarding the utilization of ChatGPT and social media platforms. To address these concerns, the authors proposed employing mathematical frameworks to capture the complexity of student experiences and ensure comprehensive evaluation processes. Furthermore, studies emphasized the importance of critical thinking and discernment among students when engaging with ChatGPT (Firaina & Sulisworo, 2023). Educators were encouraged to design assignments that foster self-reflection, critical thinking, and problem-solving (Sun & Hoelscher, 2023). It was also underscored that educators should equip students with the necessary skills to critically evaluate information and make informed decisions.

While some studies focused on the potential benefits and positive attitudes towards ChatGPT (Shoufan, 2023; Zhu et al., 2023; Katz et al., 2023; Schmidt-Fajlik, 2023; Azaria et al., 2023), others highlighted concerns regarding potential threats such as cheating, diminished critical thinking skills, and difficulties in evaluating information generated by ChatGPT (Rahman & Watanobe, 2023; Stepanechko & Kozub, 2023). These concerns underscore the necessity for responsible usage and the adaptation of teaching methodologies to effectively incorporate emerging technologies like ChatGPT. In conclusion, the literature review provides valuable insights into the attitude toward ChatGPT in English Language Teaching (ELT). While there is a positive outlook on its potential benefits, concerns regarding its limitations and potential risks must be addressed. Educators and learners should approach ChatGPT with caution and explore ways to leverage its capabilities while maintaining responsible usage. The integration of ChatGPT into ELT requires careful consideration of its impact on different language skills, the ethical implications, and the promotion of critical thinking among students.

CONCLUSION

The potential impact of ChatGPT on the landscape of English Language Teaching and Learning is immense, as it exhibits the ability to comprehend intricate queries, generate plausible responses, and offer personalized assistance. By capitalizing on ChatGPT's vast knowledge base, educators can foster creativity, cater to individual needs, and create engaging learning experiences. Nonetheless, responsible implementation remains paramount, necessitating awareness of potential risks and challenges associated with advanced technologies like ChatGPT. Furthermore, ethical considerations related to accuracy, bias, and privacy must be addressed in its integration. Despite limitations, the advantages of ChatGPT include enhanced student involvement, accessibility of resources, and adaptable learning experiences. Striking a balance between AI and human engagement is crucial, as teachers play a pivotal role in nurturing critical thinking and social skills in students.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- AI, O. (2022). *ChatGPT: Optimizing Language Models for Dialogue*. <https://openai.com/blog/chatgpt/>
- Ali, J. K. M., Shamsan, M. A. A., Hezam, T. A., & Mohammed, A. A. Q. (2023). Impact of ChatGPT on Learning Motivation: Teachers and Students' Voices. *Journal of English Studies in Arabia Felix*, 2(1), 41–49. <https://doi.org/10.56540/jesaf.v2i1.51>
- Alnaqbi, N. M., & Fouda, W. (2023). Exploring the Role of ChatGPT and social media in Enhancing Student Evaluation of Teaching Styles in Higher Education Using Neutrosophic Sets. *International Journal of Neutrosophic Science*, 20(4), 181–191. <https://doi.org/10.54216/ijns.200414>
- Azaria, A., Azoulay, R., & Reches, S. (2023). *ChatGPT is a Remarkable Tool—For Experts*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2306.03102>
- Baidoo-Anu, D., & Owusu Ansah, L. (2023). Education in the Era of Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI): Understanding the Potential Benefits of ChatGPT in Promoting Teaching and Learning. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4337484>
- Belda, J. (2022). Using Chatbots as AI Conversational Partners in Language Learning. *Applied Sciences*, 12(17), 8427. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12178427>
- Cannon, B. (2023). Learning and Teaching With ChatGPT? Interview With Morton Ann Gernsbacher, PhD. *PsychEverywhere*, 5. <https://doi.org/10.24839/psych5.05>
- Caulfield, J. (2023, February 13). *Using ChatGPT for Assignments | Tips & Examples*. Scribbr. <https://www.scribbr.com/ai-tools/chatgpt-assignments/>
- Chinonso, O. E., Theresa, A. M.-E., & Aduke, T. C. (2023). ChatGPT for Teaching, Learning and Research: Prospects and Challenges. *Global Academic Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, 5(02), 33–40. <https://doi.org/10.36348/gajhss.2023.v05i02.001>
- Farrokhnia, M., Banihashem, S. K., Noroozi, O., & Wals, A. (2023). A SWOT analysis of ChatGPT: Implications for educational practice and research. *Innovations in Education and Teaching International*, 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14703297.2023.2195846>
- Fauzi, F., Tuhuteru, L., Sampe, F., Ausat, A. M. A., & Hatta, H. R. (2023). Analysing the Role of ChatGPT in Improving Student Productivity in

- Higher Education. *Journal on Education*, 5(4), 14886–14891. <https://doi.org/10.31004/joe.v5i4.2563>
- Firaina, R., & Sulisworo, D. (2023). Exploring the Usage of ChatGPT in Higher Education: Frequency and Impact on Productivity. *Buletin Edukasi Indonesia*, 2(01), 39–46. <https://doi.org/10.56741/bei.v2i01.310>
- Fitria, T. N. (2023). Artificial intelligence (AI) technology in OpenAI ChatGPT application: A review of ChatGPT in writing English essay. *ELT Forum: Journal of English Language Teaching*, 12(1), Article 1. <https://doi.org/10.15294/elt.v12i1.64069>
- Gupta, M., & Muddgal, A. (2022). *A study: Role of artificial intelligence in education sector*. 060004. <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0103948>
- Halaweh, M. (2023). ChatGPT in education: Strategies for responsible implementation. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 15(2), ep421. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cedtech/13036>
- Herbold, S., Hautli-Janisz, A., Heuer, U., Kikteva, Z., & Trautsch, A. (2023). *AI, write an essay for me: A large-scale comparison of human-written versus ChatGPT-generated essays*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2304.14276>
- Joshi, I., Budhiraja, R., Dev, H., Kadia, J., Ataulah, M. O., Mitra, S., Kumar, D., & Akolekar, H. D. (2023). *ChatGPT – a Blessing or a Curse for Undergraduate Computer Science Students and Instructors?* <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2304.14993>
- Katz, A., Wei, S., Nanda, G., Brinton, C., & Ohland, M. (2023). *Exploring the Efficacy of ChatGPT in Analyzing Student Teamwork Feedback with an Existing Taxonomy*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2305.11882>
- Kohnke, L., Moorhouse, B. L., & Zou, D. (2023). ChatGPT for Language Teaching and Learning. *RELC Journal*, 003368822311628. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00336882231162868>
- Mageira, K., Pittou, D., Papasalouros, A., Kotis, K., Zangogianni, P., & Daradoumis, A. (2022). Educational AI Chatbots for Content and Language Integrated Learning. *Applied Sciences*, 12(7), 3239. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app12073239>
- Perkins, M. (2023). Academic integrity considerations of AI Large Language Models in the post-pandemic era: ChatGPT and beyond. *Journal of University Teaching and Learning Practice*, 20(2). <https://doi.org/10.53761/1.20.02.07>

- Qureshi, B. (2023). *Exploring the Use of ChatGPT as a Tool for Learning and Assessment in Undergraduate Computer Science Curriculum: Opportunities and Challenges*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2304.11214>
- Rahman, Md. M., & Watanobe, Y. (2023). ChatGPT for Education and Research: Opportunities, Threats, and Strategies. *Applied Sciences*, *13*(9), 5783. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13095783>
- Schmidt-Fajlik, R. (2023). ChatGPT as a Grammar Checker for Japanese English Language Learners: A Comparison with Grammarly and ProWritingAid. *AsiaCALL Online Journal*, *14*(1), 105–119. <https://doi.org/10.54855/acoj.231417>
- Shoufan, A. (2023). Exploring Students' Perceptions of ChatGPT: Thematic Analysis and Follow-Up Survey. *IEEE Access*, *11*, 38805–38818. <https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2023.3268224>
- Stepanechko, O., & Kozub, L. (2023). ENGLISH TEACHERS' CONCERNS ABOUT THE ETHICAL USE OF CHATGPT BY UNIVERSITY STUDENTS. *Grail of Science*, *25*, 297–302. <https://doi.org/10.36074/grail-of-science.17.03.2023.051>
- Sun, G. H., & Hoelscher, S. H. (2023). The ChatGPT Storm and What Faculty Can Do. *Nurse Educator*, *48*(3), 119–124. <https://doi.org/10.1097/nne.0000000000001390>
- Wahyuni, D. S. (2022). Integrated Classroom-Chatbot Experience: An Alternative Solution for English as Foreign Language Learners. *English Language Education and Current Trends (ELECT)*, 63–68. <https://doi.org/10.37301/elect.v1i1.36>
- Wardat, Y., Tashtoush, M. A., AlAli, R., & Jarrah, A. M. (2023). ChatGPT: A revolutionary tool for teaching and learning mathematics. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, *19*(7), em2286. <https://doi.org/10.29333/ejmste/13272>
- Zhu, G., Fan, X., Hou, C., Zhong, T., Seow, P., Shen-Hsing, A. C., Rajalingam, P., Yew, L. K., & Poh, T. L. (2023). *Embrace Opportunities and Face Challenges: Using ChatGPT in Undergraduate Students' Collaborative Interdisciplinary Learning*. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2305.18616>